

Task 4.4A (Subtask 5): Develop Methods to Expand Existing RADx Data Hub Metadata

Technical Report
Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

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Purpose

This technical report describes methods to improve metadata for the RADx Data Hub by reducing manual curation effort and creating a sustainable foundation for ongoing metadata maintenance. The report describes two separate efforts:

1. **Advance automation for metadata template updates.** This effort focuses on the changes applied to the RADx Data Hub metadata template and describes a software tool based on an automated workflow (the RADx Metadata Enhancement Tool) to migrate, correct, and enrich existing metadata.
2. **Strengthen study discovery with semantic technologies.** This initiative proposes a path to clarify and standardize search capabilities of the RADx Study Explorer by linking terms to controlled vocabularies and ontologies, and it provides a reproducible method for designing the controlled vocabularies that underpin RADx Data Hub search filters.

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Introduction

As the RADx Data Hub receives new data submissions, the existing metadata slowly drifts from real-world usage: fields become outdated or underutilized, critical identifiers are missing, and manual curation cannot keep pace. Sustaining high-quality discovery and reuse therefore requires infrastructure that can evolve with the data. This includes support for metadata schema updates, automated validation and correction, and smooth migration of existing records.

This report presents **practical methods and workflows for bringing RADx Data Hub metadata up to the latest standard** while improving its usefulness for search and discovery. [The updated data file metadata template](#) broadens coverage and tightens alignment with FAIR principles by adding high-value fields (e.g., dbGaP Study Page, RADx Data Hub Study Page) and removing redundant or deprecated fields. To make adoption efficient and consistent, the **RADx Metadata Enhancement Tool** automates migration of existing JSON-LD instances: validating them against [the original template](#), correcting common issues, enriching records with authoritative identifiers (e.g., ROR and ORCID), and regenerating instances that validate against the updated template. The workflow relies on established components, namely the **RADx Metadata Validator** and the **RADx-rad Metadata Compiler**, and outputs a complete, template-conformant set of metadata files.

Beyond template migration, the report addresses findability in the **Study Explorer**. It proposes representing filter categories and values with semantic technologies, such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies to clarify metadata terms, enabling consistent annotation, interoperability, and more precise search. We also describe a systematic and reproducible method for constructing and updating such controlled vocabularies as the needs for the metadata schema in the RADx Data Hub evolve.

A Tool for RADx Metadata Enhancement

Overview

The Stanford team has updated [the original data file metadata template](#) through the addition of new fields and elements, the removal of unused fields, and structural refinements. These updates broaden metadata coverage, better reflect real-world usage, and strengthen alignment with FAIR data principles, thereby improving findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. For instance, we added the **dbGaP Study Page** and **RADx Data Hub Study Page** fields to help users locate the corresponding study when accessing an individual data file. Conversely, we removed the **Data File Temporal Coverage** and **Data File Spatial Coverage** elements due to the absence of input. Further details are provided in the report [4.4A-4 – Technical Report: Update and Extend the RADx Data Hub Metadata Schema](#).

To streamline the adoption of these updates, the Stanford team developed the **RADx Metadata Enhancement Tool** to automate the update process. The tool processes existing metadata files, aligns them with the updated template, corrects inconsistencies, and expands metadata content using both existing and derived information. By automating this workflow, the tool reduces manual effort, ensures consistent quality, and accelerates the transition to the updated metadata template.

Metadata Enhancement Workflow

The Stanford team developed the workflow around the RADx Metadata Enhancement Tool to provide an automated process for updating metadata instances. As the CEDAR metadata template evolves, we need to update existing instances to remain consistent with the latest version. This workflow addresses that need by validating original metadata, applying corrections where necessary, and generating updated instances.

Figure 1. Metadata Enhancement Workflow.

Inputs

1. **Templates (JSON).** Original and updated CEDAR metadata templates.
2. **Metadata Files (JSON-LD).** All existing data file metadata in the RADx Data Hub are stored as CEDAR metadata instances, structured in JSON-LD format, and aligned with the original RADx metadata template.
3. **Original-Updated Fields Mapping (Excel).** A mapping between field names from the two template versions. It is used to guide transformation from the original template to the updated template.

Processing workflow in the tool

Step 1: Validate original metadata. Each input metadata file undergoes validation against the original template.

Step 2: Correct original metadata (if validation fails). If a file fails validation, we need to correct it manually before being reprocessed.

Step 3: Update metadata. The tool builds a new metadata instance structure for each metadata file based on the updated template. Values are either carried over from the original metadata instances or newly added. The tool first retrieves

existing values from the original metadata instances, and reformates them when needed (e.g., converting *Date* to *DateTime*). It then derives newly added values from existing information and uses them to populate additional fields introduced in the updated template. Added metadata includes:

- **ROR and ORCID Identifiers:** Although contributor names (individual and organizational) are recorded, many entries lack corresponding ROR and ORCID identifiers. To improve interoperability and traceability, the Stanford team manually retrieves identifiers by searching the ROR and ORCID registries using the provided names. The retrieved identifiers are then supplied to the tool, which uses them to populate the related fields in the updated metadata.
- **dbGaP Study Page:** Links each dataset to its corresponding study entry in the dbGaP repository. This linkage is increasingly important in light of the data transition plan, ensuring that researchers can locate the relevant study when accessing or evaluating associated data files. The tool automatically populates this link using the PHS number.
- **RADx Data Hub Study Page:** Provides a direct link to the study's overview page within the RADx Data Hub. This connection becomes increasingly important due to the data transition plan, ensuring that researchers can locate the study when accessing individual data files. The tool automatically populates this link using the study ID.

Step 4: Validate updated metadata. Once the tool finishes updating, it validates the updated metadata against the new template. The final output includes only metadata instances that pass this validation step.

Outputs

The tool produces a complete set of updated metadata files in JSON-LD format, each fully aligned with the updated template and passing validation.

Dependencies

The Metadata Enhancement Tool relies on several existing tools previously developed for the RADx Data Hub:

- **RADx Metadata Validator** – A tool specifically developed for RADx to automatically validate metadata files against a given template. It is used in the enhancement process to check metadata before and after updates.
- **RADx-rad Metadata Compiler** – A tool for converting RADx-rad CSV metadata into JSON-LD. Certain components are reused within the enhancement tool.

The RADx Metadata Validator and RADx-rad Metadata Compiler have been described earlier in the technical report - [RADx Data Hub Metadata Toolkit](#).

Future Work

Some values for newly added fields and elements in the updated template require direct analysis of the underlying data files. This functionality is not yet developed due to original limitations in accessing the data files. Examples include **sample properties, descriptive statistics, and file format**.

Method for Enhancing Metadata Values used in the RADx Data Hub Study Explorer

Overview

The **Study Explorer** in the [RADx Data Hub supports study and variable discovery](#) through free-text search and flexible filter options. Filters are used to narrow search results with respect to a set of predefined **categories** (e.g., *Study Population Focus, RADx Data Program*). Each category contains one or more **values** that specify the concrete criteria used to narrow results. For example, *Study Population Focus* offers the values, **Adults, Children, and Older Adults or Elderly** to restrict results to studies on different age groups.

The effectiveness of both text- and filter-based discovery depends on the quality and completeness of the underlying metadata and filter definitions. The next section highlights ways to enhance the available filters and their corresponding values.

Filter Options in the Study Explorer

The filter categories in the **Study Explorer** are similar to those in the [database of Genotypes and Phenotypes \(dbGaP\)](#), such as *Study Design*, *NIH Institute*, and *Study Subject Count*. In the RADx Data Hub, there are **nine filter categories**:

1. Study Population Focus
2. Sample Size Range
3. Study Domain
4. Study Design
5. Data Collection Method
6. NIH Institute / Center
7. RADx Data Program
8. Has Data Files
9. Study Variables

Each category contains a fixed set of filter values (which can be quite numerous, up to 87 in the case of *Study Variables*). All 187 available studies in the RADx Data Hub are annotated with respect to these categories and their associated values, ensuring **consistent dataset annotation** and enabling structured search in the Study Explorer.

Effective filtering with the approach outlined above assumes users already understand both the organization of available filter categories and the meaning of their values. However, there is no shared conceptual model for the filters, and there exists no documentation that defines the values or explains their rationale. This gap is especially problematic when acronyms, abbreviations, or domain-specific terms appear without context. Examples include:

- **Study Domain:** *Novel Biosensing or VOC*
- **Study Design:** *Time-Series*
- **Data Collection Method:** *Real-World Data*
- **Study Variables:**
 - *nih_copd*
 - *nih_nopd_plus*
 - *nih_cf*
 - *nih_cld_bpd*

- *nih_othermh*

For many users, it won't be obvious that **VOC** means "volatile organic compounds," that **Time-Series** refers to an **Interrupted Time Series** design, or why **Real-World Data** is treated as a data-collection method. There is a clear need to standardize and clarify the meaning of the underlying metadata model. A more formal representation of filters categories and values can address these issues by including precise labels, definitions, synonyms, brief usage notes, and other relevant information.

Semantic technologies enable this formal, richer representation by giving every filter and value a persistent identifier that can be associated with precise labels, definitions, synonyms, aliases, etc. Furthermore, conceptual relationships can be captured and documented explicitly with knowledge representation languages, which paves the way for semantic search capabilities as well as interoperability with external resources. The next section details these benefits.

Enhancing Filter Options with Semantic Technologies

Controlled vocabularies and **ontologies** offer standardized representations of terms that help clarify and disambiguate their meaning. For example, a study variable such as *nih_copd* can be linked to a unique identifier that explains the acronym *COPD* (*chronic obstructive pulmonary disease*) and provides connections to related terms such as *nih_copd_plus*. This enables RADx Data Hub users to look up and understand filter options and values, allowing them to construct searches more effectively. Figure 2 below shows how the concept *Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease* is represented in the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) vocabulary.

Figure 2. Example identifier in the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) vocabulary for *Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease* as displayed in [BioPortal](#).

Beyond clarifying acronyms and abbreviations, linking to established vocabularies and ontologies can also provide **valuable context for interpreting terms**. For instance, the filter value *Time Series* under the *Study Design* category might be mistaken for its general mathematical meaning, namely a series of data points ordered over time. In this case, however, it actually refers to a specific study design based on *Interrupted Time Series Analysis*. By connecting such terms to authoritative vocabularies and ontologies (see Figure 3), users can look up their precise, context-appropriate meaning, **avoiding ambiguity and user confusion**.

Figure 3: Example representation of “Time Series” in the “Medical Subject Headings” ontology (MeSH) as displayed in [BioPortal](#).

The potential of semantic technologies to enhance metadata management in the RADx Data Hub, particularly within the Study Explorer raises key questions: What filter values can be linked to semantic technologies? What filter values would need to be changed? Which controlled vocabularies and ontologies should be used? Are new resources required? If so, how should they be designed? We will examine these questions in the next section.

Method for Expanding Metadata

Designing metadata to index domain-specific data, such as COVID-19 studies in the RADx Data Hub, requires a clear understanding of the available content so that relevant information can be effectively captured as metadata. Many of the current filter values in the Study Explorer have been manually derived from plain-text sources, including study descriptions, experimental reports, and excerpts from associated publications.

Ideally, this process should follow a more systematic approach, with clear documentation of the source material and well-defined methods for extracting relevant terms. Such an approach involves three distinct phases:

1. **Collecting** the relevant input data
2. **Extracting** meaningful keywords from the collected data
3. **Selecting** a final set of keywords to include in a metadata model for dataset annotation

Each phase should be designed for reproducibility and repeatability, ensuring that the metadata model can be efficiently updated as new data is submitted to the Data Hub over time.

In the following, we treat a general metadata model as a finite collection of *attributes*, each with a defined *set of permissible values*, grouped by conceptual relatedness. For example, the Study Explorer's **Study Population Focus** filter establishes the scope for related metadata. Within this filter, values should follow a clear conceptual model: age-related values (e.g., *Children, Adults, Older Adults*) are grouped together and kept distinct from population descriptors such as ethnicity or race (e.g., *Asian, Hispanic/Latino, African American*). This organization helps users select and combine filters appropriately.

The mentioned conceptual model should be grounded in the data available in the RADx Data Hub and should be derived from the actual study data, so the metadata both faithfully exposes what information exists and provides clear access paths to it (e.g., via filters, facets, and navigable groupings).

Collecting Input Data

To derive meaningful metadata attributes and their associated values, the first step is to identify the *source materials containing the relevant information*. The data collection protocol should clearly define:

- **Scope:** Which materials are considered in-scope.
- **Rationale:** Why these materials were selected.
- **Methodology:** How information will be extracted to ensure traceability and reproducibility.

For example, when curating metadata related to *Study Population Focus*, source materials may include the *Methods* or *Study Design* sections of study reports, study protocols, or clinical trial registry entries. These sections often specify critical

descriptors such as age groups, race/ethnicity categories, and other population characteristics.

Extracting Keywords

Once the input materials for all relevant components of the metadata model have been collected and organized by their specific applicability, the plain text from each document should be extracted and analyzed to identify *key terms* and *phrases*. These should then be grouped into semantic categories that capture related concepts and align directly with the corresponding elements of the metadata model. This can be done using tools such as [KeyBERT](#) or large language models (LLM) to identify salient keywords in free text and to discover important metadata categories that are not yet captured in an existing metadata model. For existing metadata values, a more structured representation allows for the extraction of more targeted metadata. For example the current values for the Study Population Focus can be organized into the following categories:

- **Age:**
 - Adults
 - Children
 - Older Adults or Elderly
- **Race/Ethnicity:**
 - Racial or Ethnic Minorities
 - Hispanics or Latinos
 - African Americans
 - Asians
 - Native Hawaiians or Other Pacific Islanders
- **Social Context:**
 - Sexual or Gender Minorities
 - Immigrants
 - Lower Socioeconomic Status (SES) Populations
 - Homeless or Unhoused Populations
 - Rural Communities
 - School Communities
 - Essential Workers

- Incarcerated or Institutionalized Populations
- Underserved or Vulnerable Populations
- **Health:**
 - People Living with HIV/AIDS
 - Dialysis Patients
 - Intellectual or Developmental Disabilities
 - Pregnant or Nursing Women

With an initial taxonomy in place, tools for Named Entity Recognition (NER), such as [GLiNER](#) and LLMs can be used to extract candidate values from free text (e.g., study titles, descriptions, reports, etc.) for specific categories. These candidate values can then be analyzed to identify gaps in the existing value sets. For example, the current representation of the concept “**Age**” includes only three values. Signals for finer granularity arise when study materials explicitly mention age-related target demographics *not covered* by the present set. The dbGaP study phs002647, *Supporting COVID-19 prevention and testing for marginalized and minoritized **youth and young adults***, illustrates this pattern: recurring references to “young adults” across multiple studies provide a data-driven basis for adding an additional value such as “Young Adult.”

Selecting Keywords for Metadata Expansion

Given the identified set of categories, keywords, and key phrases aligned with specific components of the metadata model, the extracted information must be systematically analyzed and harmonized. This involves mapping the raw textual data to a representative terminology that can be formalized into a controlled vocabulary. A well-defined vocabulary ensures consistency, clarity, and precision in metadata annotation across datasets.

Term harmonization is achieved by combining automated mapping tools (e.g., [text2term](#)) with established vocabularies such as the **Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)** thesaurus. In this workflow, free-text keywords and phrases are mapped to MeSH concepts, allowing semantically equivalent expressions to resolve to a single identifier. This alignment groups related terms under a unified entry and improves interoperability and search performance. Continuing with the example for the “**Age**”

concept, references to older adults, such as “elderly,” “seniors,” “senior citizens,” “aged 80 and over,” “geriatric population”, would map to *one preferred term* in the RADx Data Hub’s controlled vocabulary, supporting consistent dataset annotation.

Figure 4 summarizes the workflow from text input sources to final metadata annotations.

Figure 4: Text-to-Metadata Pipeline. Workflow to develop, expand, and maintain a data-driven metadata model.

Conclusion

In this report, we have presented two main initiatives to improve metadata in the RADx Data Hub by reducing manual curation and creating a sustainable foundation for ongoing maintenance.

The first initiative advances automation for metadata template updates through the RADx Metadata Enhancement Tool, which enables efficient migration, correction, and enrichment of existing records. The second initiative strengthens study discovery in the RADx Study Explorer by applying semantic technologies that link filter values to controlled vocabularies and ontologies, providing a reproducible

method for designing and maintaining these resources. Together, these efforts enhance the quality, interoperability, and findability of RADx Data Hub metadata, ensuring that the platform remains adaptable and valuable for future research.

The methods, workflows, and tools in this report provide a practical approach for designing and sustaining metadata models and their data annotations. The approach includes (1) identifying meaningful metadata attributes from source data, (2) deriving and iteratively refining models linked to controlled vocabularies, and (3) maintaining consistent, valid annotations as the model evolves with new submissions. While developed for the RADx Data Hub, the approach is domain-agnostic and broadly applicable to repositories pursuing FAIR principles. By aligning metadata with controlled vocabularies and using updatable CEDAR templates to capture machine-actionable annotations, our methods reduce curation effort, support reproducible analyses, and improve the discoverability and reuse of public datasets. Ultimately, these contributions advance the long-term sustainability of the RADx Data Hub and promote Open Science across disciplines.

Resources

1. RADx Metadata Enhancement Tool GitHub:
<https://github.com/bmir-radx/radx-metadata-converter>
2. Metadata template (new):
<https://openview.metadatascenter.org/templates/https:%2F%2Frepo.metadatascenter.org%2Ftemplates%2Fdb374683-f15b-4f87-8279-84f5bf057f5c>
3. Metadata template (original):
<https://openview.metadatascenter.org/templates/https:%2F%2Frepo.metadatascenter.org%2Ftemplates%2Fc691629c-1183-4425-9a12-26201eab1a10>
4. 4.4A-4 – Technical Report: Update and Extend the RADx Data Hub Metadata Schema:
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1yz_IQt7mcM3gTC5zx4XLYI7obGq0fOE5/view
5. RADx Data Hub Metadata Toolkit:
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bKTuvBCfZh3kSw9fTH3FQhzMghnqOGAZXx5LeVXiSlc/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.p134wx7n6xor>
6. RADx Data Hub Search Interface Documentation:
<https://radxdatahub.nih.gov/gettingStarted>
7. database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP):
<https://dbgap.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/home>
8. BioPortal: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>
9. KeyBERT: <https://github.com/MaartenGr/KeyBERT>
10. GLiNER: <https://github.com/urchade/GLiNER>
11. text2term: <https://github.com/rsgoncalves/text2term>